

THE ONTOLOGY OF THE LANGUAGE-SPEECH DIALECTIC IN THE PROCESS OF REASONING

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Annotation. The article seeks to justify the main epistemological specificity of the process of thinking. In addition, the influence of language and speech on the development of science has been revealed. The important aspect of this article is that the current philosophical aspects of the development of science are highlighted from a dialectical point of view.

Key words: causality, practice and language, sense organs, abstract thinking, imagination, language and thinking about the world, thinking.

The language, which can reflect the experiences of the past generations, will attract the individual from the moment he is born and influences his psyche. The adults, who name things for them, or teach the names of the things to the children, inevitably design the outer world for the children, and children adopt verbal and lexical meaning systems from adults. And this means the complete reorganization of the psychic processes in children. It creates new forms of attention, memory, representation, reflection and motion.

Intuition and other sensory forms of cognition are understood through practice and language, that is, they are one of the forms of consciousness. So what is awareness or consciousness? Let's briefly touch on this issue. Because this issue is of great importance in fully understanding the essence of the issues discussed in the book. S.L. Rubinshtsyin is one of the scientists who worked on this problem on the basis of rich materials. According to him, consciousness is a subject's awareness of objective existence and is characterized by the following features:

Consciousness is one of the higher forms of psyche. It appears from the time when a person can distinguish himself as a person from the world around him. The emergence of consciousness is connected with the emergence of speech, the generalization of world realities reflected in it. This is related to the ability of the word to generalize and store the acquired knowledge in the language. It is self-evident that language, considered as the second signal system, is of great importance here, because it is the biological basis of the subject's self-awareness, and this process also relies on practice. The second signal system makes it possible to distinguish between material and ideal events, the subject of knowledge is opposed to its object.

Thus, we said that sensory perception is realized consciously, assuming that practice and language leave the function of sensory organs in social traces, and abstract thinking and language affect intuition and imagination, as well as social practice. Conscious perception is fundamentally different from the function of animal sensory organs. . It should be mentioned that the brain of a higher animal can also reflect certain complex phenomena, even to a certain extent causal relationships. But this perception is unconscious and cannot go beyond conditioned reflexes. In a person, experience, the outside world acquires a new meaning. The ability to actively influence the outside world, which is completely foreign to animals, appears

People cannot think without the help of concepts, discussions and conclusions, which are the basic forms of abstract thinking associated with language. But imagination is not thought, but the emotional form of consciousness, that is, only the material for thought. Logical thinking appears only when concepts formed in words arise based on imagination. Imagination depends not directly on language, but through the thought of words. This means that the connection between the concept and the word consists of the connection of two signal systems that are qualitatively different from each other and interact with each other.

Investigators who believe that imagination is directly related to language ignore the distinction between emotional cognition and mental cognition. In doing so, they underestimate the role of language in the dialectical transition from imagination to understanding.

Therefore, the imagination associated with language cannot be considered as a form of knowledge expressed in the form of the material shell of the word.

Imagination cannot be the meaning of the word, it can only enter into a special relationship with the meaning of the word. Forming and developing imagination becomes a concept, not a word meaning, with the help of language. According to linguistic data, the experiments conducted with children show that when the first words are grammatically formed, that is, until the concept is expressed in them, N.I. Krasnogorsky states: "this is a physiological way of transition: external or internal stimulation - the formation of a conditioned reflex in it - mediating this reflex with words (the emergence of a speech-moving reflex) - the formation of speech chains and streams - this is thinking. A complete coherent collection of speech chains is an idea.

Man perceives the world as a generalized social practice based on language and thought. The second signal system connects emotional cognition in this way with

private and social experience. A person's attention and goal-oriented pursuit are also very important. For example, suppose two people are examining one person's eyes. One of them is an ophthalmologist, and the second is completely ignorant of anatomy and physiology. In this, of course, a specialist (doctor - ophthalmologist) notices a lot more than the second person. Social practice, first of all, created the need for exchange of ideas and communication among working people. This need led to the formation of language, that is, the second signal system. Naturally, the words that appear in the language have a specific meaning, different from ordinary sounds in nature. Otherwise, words cannot be a tool for communication, expression of thoughts, exchange of ideas.

The emergence of language was a great leap in the development of higher nervous activity, adding new principles to the nervous system and brain activity. So, the connection of both signaling systems is the basis of two stages of cognition, that is, emotional cognition and rational cognition.

A person's normal imagination appears only under the control of the second signal system, which corresponds to the relations of the objective world. Thinking is formed on the basis of the same complex neural connections, associations of these connections. "Thought," said I.I. Pavlov is nothing but associations, first the elements that come into contact with external objects, and then the associations that form the whole chain. Therefore, every small, first association consists of the moment of birth of thought. The neural connections formed in the human brain form the material substrate of thinking. These relationships are formed on the basis of experience, and are also important in terms of being the basis for new experience, creating conditions for practical impact on existence.

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